

PROJECT TITLE

CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS: SMART GRID

Author - Gifty Acquah

Abstract

The smart grid is an extremely complex system of immense importance in people's modern lives. The modernisation of the smart grid has a direct impact on economic, political, and social aspects. While the modernisation of the electricity infrastructure has many benefits, it also brings many new threats. In addition, one must consider the increasing number of attacks on the smart grid, such as cyber security attacks, physical blackouts, and false data injection attacks. This article will describe how sensor monitoring can be used to improve the security of the smart grid, as well as Internet-based change attacks against the smart grid. Finally, future developments and potential problems for the smart grid are presented and discussed.

Keywords

Smart Grid; Grid modernization; Vulnerability; Cyber Attack; Blackout; False Data Injection Attack; Load-Altering Attack (LAA); Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA); Public Key Infrastructure (PKI)

1. Introduction

The power grid is an interconnected network that is used to transport electricity from producers to consumers. It consists of power stations, substations (to raise or lower the voltage), electricity transmission (to transport electricity over long distances), and distribution (to lower the voltage to the service voltage required by the customer). Currently, the grid uses a limited one-way exchange, which means that electricity flows from the power plant to the consumer. The smart grid, on the other hand, introduces the concept of two-way switching. (DiGiuse, 2017) In a smart grid system, both electricity and information can be exchanged in both directions between the consumer and the electricity company. In contrast to the efficiency and stability of the smart grid, the power grid has little storage capacity. In addition, smart grids are more environmentally friendly than conventional grids. It can incorporate wind and solar energy into the operation of the grid.

Figure 1. Traditional grids vs. smart grids in various aspects

("Smart grids: electricity networks and the grid in evolution", 2022)

Figure 2. Overview of smart grid ("Smart Grid Technology Working Operation and Applications", 2022)

1.1. How Smart Grid Works (Distributed network)

A smart grid can often be defined as a smart grid that combines intelligent digital communication technology with a power grid. The distributed network technologies used in smart grids are used in a wide range of applications and usually fall into several key technology areas: 1) Smart appliances, whose ground systems are set to determine when energy is consumed based on the customer's needs and preferences. 2) Smart meters, which typically provide two-way communication between the customer and the electricity supplier, not only allow maintenance personnel to get to the location of faults more quickly and

accurately to service equipment but also automatically collect data for costing purposes. 3) Smart substations, which serve to detect and control operational data, perform multiple voltage transformations at various locations and transmit power safely and reliably to customers. In addition to this, smart substations also split the current path in multiple directions. 4) Superconducting cables, which are often used for long-distance power transmission and can be used for prediction and fault analysis based on real-time conditions. 5) Integrated communications, which is the key to smart grid technology, uses a variety of different technologies to communicate and keep the needs of the system coordinated ("Smart Grid Technology Working Operation and Applications", 2022).

Figure 3. Smart grid components

("Smart Grid Technology Working Operation and Applications", 2022)

1.2. Resilience of a System

Systems have a property called resilience. It's the ability to respond to and recover from adversity. Vulnerability, adaptation, and resilience are the three fundamental components of resilience. Nowadays, smart grids are invariably vulnerable to a variety of threats, and countermeasures are being made to protect them. Redundancy, flexibility, and spoofing, for example, are engineering approaches to improving the resilience of smart grids. To improve system resilience, interdependent essential infrastructure is also used to boost resilience.

2. Grid Modernization – Smart Grid

To achieve a national-level smart grid system, the grid needs to be modernized first. The power systems and power facilities in countries with an early industrialization process are usually quite outdated. With the advent of technologies such as sensors, computing technology, communication technology and blockchain, the process of modernizing the grid has been accelerated (Miller, et al. 2014). This includes the development of safer, more efficient, and even more commercially profitable distributed and renewable energy sources, electrical energy storage technologies, monitoring, protection and self-healing capabilities, automation, and control devices, as well as smart meters and electric vehicles on the customer side. Due to the integration of distributed energy sources, the obsolete grid needs to address many issues. For example, 1. bi-directional currents at the power plant and customer side 2. management of the current-voltage 3. low fault currents and the need for adequate isolation of faults 4. system inertia problems with frequency regulation 5 inefficient system maintenance operations etc. (Tan, 2016)

The new generation of smart grids needs to enable bi-directional communication between meters and utilities to take on the task of data collection, metering, and transmission. Metering through smart meters enables two-way communication and ensures more accurate billing. As the basis for advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), smart meters provide customers with more detailed information about their electricity consumption and control their energy usage (Tan, 2017). Thanks to AMI, utilities can provide an effective communication network for service points with accurate addresses more quickly, and customers' devices can be connected to the entire grid system quickly. Thanks to upgrades in transformer and feeder detection, outage management, electric vehicle integration and fault isolation technology, AMI and distribution automation are rapidly evolving and are the prelude to grid modernization (Hart, 2012).

Before the modernization of the electricity network, the distribution system was designed only with the need to meet peak demand (provided quality demand was met) as a one-way passive infrastructure, delivering energy to consumers. Today the needs of customers have changed, increased customers want a balance between their electricity consumption and the amount of electricity generated by the power plant. They want to be able to send excess electricity back to the grid and be paid for it (Manning, 2015). But when it is needed, the power plant can send the excess back to the grid. To meet the needs of consumers, both the storage technology and the structure of the distribution network need to be changed. The following is the modern planning and operation of the Transmission and Distribution system (T&D). The net load on the distribution system will increase as it grows, necessitating improved coordination and information transfer between distributed systems. The system

no longer uses simple load forecasts to predict net load but must also be able to forecast photovoltaic generation. the T&D system provides an aggregated energy supply from distributed energy sources (DER) and can provide ancillary services to the wholesale electricity market. the visibility and controllability of the DER are essential to the overall smart grid (Manning, 2015).

Distribution system technology needs to be more flexible, and more reliable and provide DER hosting by replacing it with new facilities that can support distributed generation and dynamic control of electronic storage. The distribution system of the future will be able to provide secure, resilient, and reliable services and operate a highly dynamic distribution grid associated with high DER penetration scenarios (Tuballa, 2016). To achieve this, the modernization of the grid will require workforce development and the development of a workforce that can cope with grid changes and is familiar with smart grid operations.

3. Threat Vector of Modernization

While modernising the electricity infrastructure has numerous benefits, it also has the potential to introduce new threats. Consider the following scenario:

Smart grids will transmit large amounts of sensitive customer information. Some IT professionals believe that cyber-attacks increasingly pose a threat to national energy and information systems. And many vulnerabilities go unreported to keep cyber intrusions from affecting reputations. The smart grid could trigger a cyber-attack through the grid rather than on the grid itself, a hitherto unknown form of attack in the energy sector. (Pearson,

2011) The smart grid will transmit much more sensitive customer information than the traditional grid. When an attacker accesses the victim's information through the grid as a channel, this sensitive information is subject to possible compromise, and there may be coercion and blackmail to threaten the victim. In addition, the European Commission has pointed out that smart metering technology may allow system operators to reduce customer demand to balance the grid during an incident. This undoubtedly poses a challenge to customer experience and customer information.

A lot of devices are controlled in the smart grid. The smart grid's demand for devices has grown exponentially compared to the traditional grid people use today. These devices will control the supply and demand of electricity throughout the system. Many sensors are in the system, which will help the operators identify traffic and special conditions to ensure the reliable operation of the grid. Every device in the system will inevitably be connected to the network to become a node in the system, and these nodes will inevitably become theoretical access points. This undoubtedly increases the penetration of the smart grid system by attackers. At the same time, the larger scale of the system and the redundancy of devices present a challenge for monitoring and supervision. Some estimate that the future smart grid will be 100 to 1000 times larger than the internet (LaMonica, 2018).

A large proportion of devices in the smart grid have poor physical security. In an actual smart grid system, a large proportion of devices will be assigned to more uncomfortable physical locations than ever before, such as customers' homes or even on the street. Devices that need to collect data in the field, such as smart meters, are placed in physical environments where security is not guaranteed. Take smart meters, for example, they are often installed in the customer's home or in proximity to the customer's house. This

certainly makes it easier for attackers with ulterior motives. The attacker can easily access the target and gain undue profits. In addition, the security of the devices themselves is also at risk. The built-in security of conventional computers cannot be guaranteed. Because conventional personal computers are designed to operate in isolated environments without external network connections, they often do not have any built-in security. These computers will monitor large geographical areas of the grid, which means there are many entry points into the network. Those computers used for smart grids will need to address these security issues (Metke & Ekl, 2010).

There are deficiencies in smart grid communication and hardware standards. So far, the main communication standard in smart grid systems is the Internet Protocol (IP). Compared to other communication standards, IP does have the advantage of flexibility. It can accommodate the development of smart grids into yet unforeseen application areas. At the same time, as a popular network standard, it has many well-known vulnerabilities. In addition to the problems with IP as a communication standard, the smart grid has a long-standing problem. If the existing grid components were to be completely upgraded, this would be a huge cost. So, the mainstream approach now is to use a wide range of commercial off-the-shelf hardware and software. This has led to different components having their own set of communication protocols or standards, with interoperability and affordability being challenged. In addition, this has led to the fact that launching an attack on a smart grid vulnerability will no longer require expertise or detailed knowledge of it. (Pearson, 2011) As these commercial hardware and software, vulnerabilities will also apply to the smart grid, an attacker only needs to know about these vulnerabilities from the

internet and commercial networks to launch an effective and widespread attack on the smart grid.

Transmission over non-uniform media poses a significant challenge to the implementation of smart grids. A large amount of data and information associated with monitoring and control will be transmitted between smart grids via the wireless communication infrastructure, which will increase radio frequency (RF) interference and competition on the limited and already very congested radio spectrum. During transmission, signals from the smart grid do not have priority over all other signals. If a signal with a higher priority propagates at the same time as the Smart Grid information, the Smart Grid signal must switch to another spectral aperture. This happens randomly and such random interruptions will inevitably lead to packet loss and delayed delivery of data. The lost packets could be any essential information. Also, communication failures in the communication channel can significantly reduce the reliability of distributed energy control in the distribution network. In the grid, communication failures can have a serious impact on the operation and control of the system and can interrupt the wide-area damping control of the power system. As a heterogeneous convergence of infinite media, communication signals in the smart grid are also exposed to multiple threats such as interference with wireless signals, damage to equipment (e.g., tampering or malfunction), and spoofing of wireless routers through denial of service (DoS) or malicious data injection. (Nghia Le, Chin & Chen, 2017)

4. Attacks on Smart Grid

Cyber Attack on the Ukrainian Power Grid

Ukraine's power grid cyber-attack on December 23 was hailed as a watershed moment in cyber security. It is the first known hacker-caused power outage, as well as the most complicated cyber-attack on infrastructure (Cyber Security & Tereza Pultarova, 2016). Due to the attack, Ukraine's power grid was down for three hours (Lee et al., 2016). The distribution grid was damaged by the cyber-attack, forcing the electrical distribution company to resort to manual mode. The SCADA system's data is transmitted through the intranet or the internet, making it more vulnerable to security breaches (Cai et al., 2008). Hence the attacker was able to remotely manage the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems.

According to the Ministry of Energy and Coal Industry of Ukraine (2016), the attack was directed at the distribution level of three Ukrainian power supply firms, resulting in the loss of power for about 225,000 customers in diverse areas.

Because of the effects of the attack on customers, the government and other private security organisations conducted a thorough investigation, concluding that it was a cyber-attack and that Russian security services were to blame (Lee et al., 2016).

Six months before the major incident, the attackers utilised social engineering to get access to knowledge about the information network and other software used, compromising the three companies' information networks. This was done to destroy servers, control switches at distribution substations, and target call centre phone numbers (*Ministry of Energy and Coal Industry of Ukraine, 2016*).

They gained a foothold by gaining access to the Industrial Control Systems (ICS) before the event by using the Black Energy Trojan to obtain administrative credentials, which they then used to run Disakil on the computer. Disakil is malware that overwrites the MBR (Master Boot Record) and other files with junk data to destroy the SCADA systems' network connections (Johnson, 2016).

The 2003 North-East Blackout in the US and Canada

The 2003 North-east Blackout knocked off power for fifty million people for four days, resulting in economic damages of between \$4 billion and \$10 billion (FERC, 2004; Knake, 2017). The incident was the second-largest power outage in history at the time (Alhelou et al., 2019; Owens, 2019). The lack of electricity not only turned off the lights, but also caused airports, subways, trains, and tunnels to close. Automatic doors, elevators, and whole drinking water utilities were all shut off due to a power outage. It caused hospitals to rely on backup generators to provide minimal power (George Mason University, 2022).

After a six-month investigation, the US Task Force discovered that due to a failure of the alarm processor in the control system, the control room operators at FirstEnergy, an Ohio-based electric utility, were unable to have enough situational awareness of critical operational changes to the electrical grid. When many critical transmission lines in northern Ohio tripped due to contact with trees, a cascade failure of 508 producing units at 265 power facilities across eight states and Canada ensued (FERC, 2004; George Mason University, 2022).

In addition, the U.S Task Force found the below also as a cause:

- Failure to ensure operation within secure limits
- Inadequate vegetation management
- Inadequate operator training
- Failure to recognise and transmit emergency circumstances to neighbouring systems
- Inadequate regional-scale view over the bulk power system

The US Task Force advised that the above problem be solved through comprehensiveness, monitoring, training, and enforcement of dependability requirements where necessary to ensure compliance.

In addition, according to Knake (2017), the power grid's security, as well as a deterrent posture that would deter adversaries from targeting it, must be upgraded to prevent future attacks. The goal of such a plan should be to defend the electrical grid by safeguarding it, detecting attempts to undermine its security, and assuring enemies that the US will be able to identify and respond promptly to any attack.

False Data Injection Attacks

False data injection is an attack against the electric power grid's state estimation (Bobba et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2011; Niemira et al., 2013). Such attacks can introduce arbitrary mistakes into specific state variables without being recognised by existing algorithms if the attacker has access to current power system configuration information and can modify the measurements of metres at physically protected places such as substations (Liu et al., 2011).

The Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, which monitors and controls the power grid's integrated network, collects data from network sensors and feeds it into the State Estimator, which estimates the state of the power grid. This estimation of the status is used by grid operators to execute corrective control actions and plan for potential emergencies. Because the estimate is critical to the Power Grid's reliability, attackers try to tamper with sensor measurements, inject false control commands, and delay measurements and control commands. (Bobba et al., 2010; Niemira et al., 2013). The attacker uses these techniques to alter the state estimation result and modify it predictably (Liu et al., 2011).

For this attack, researchers have provided a mitigation technique. X. Liu et al. (2015) propose the Spy Domain in conjunction with secret information and an event log as an intrusion detection system in Advance Metre Infrastructure to detect false data injection; this will detect illegal readings and scribbling to manipulate data in the AMI networks. Also, according to Y. Liu et al. (2011), sensor measurement manipulation must be avoided, either by physically tampering with the device or by meddling with the connection between the sensor and the control centre. This can be accomplished by securing them against unauthorised access (both physically and remotely), as well as authenticating and protecting the sensor's measurements.

5. How Sensor Monitoring Can Improve Smart Grid Security

Sensors perform well in both protecting and improving the efficiency of smart grids. Sensors provide uninterrupted monitoring of the grid and can handle power management of DERs to improve the reliability of the grid (Vazque, 2017) By monitoring the electrical parameters of the infrastructure in the grid through sensors, it is possible to quickly detect the location of a short circuit in the event of a short circuit in the grid. This new relay-based smart sensor can

locally detect a short circuit in the shortest possible time and isolate the area so that the rest of the system can still work stably (Anderson, 1998). To detect faults such as short circuits in the grid, smart sensors will have current monitoring devices for measuring the current in the grid. The VALUE of this current is compared with the threshold current in the protection device. The purpose of this is to distinguish whether the current is caused by a fault or not.

Each intelligent sensor contains an adaptive protection scheme that is self-healing and can communicate with other coordinated sensors that detect faults and optimize setting parameters. (Alonso, 2020) The intelligent sensors perform automatic calculations based on the optimum parameters and fault measurements to automatically derive the optimum disconnection duration for the network circuit breakers. The disconnection and reactivation commands are then sent to the circuit breakers. The labelling of information within the sensor and other coordination sensors and network circuit breakers is based on the IEC 61850 standard (CNSS, 2016)

This is a relay-based sensor that needs to measure more parameters to be more useful in a smart grid, such as circuit voltage, phase and environmental temperature. This enables fluctuations in different parameters to be detected in real-time in the grid and errors can be managed and corrected at any time, allowing the grid to remain reliable under fault conditions (Kayastha, 2014). The measurement data from the sensors can all be read by the smart device with a record of the time and sensor location for each event. The current value obtained by measuring the sensor is noted as I and then the RMS value is calculated. the RMS value is in the basic component microprocessor of the sensor (MPU). This RMS value is then compared with the threshold current and when this measured value i is higher than the

threshold current then the sensor detects a fault. A GOOSE message is then sent to the next intelligent sensor $i+1$ via the communication module. If a fault is also present in $i+1$, a GOOSE message occurs to both the previous sensor i and the next sensor $i+2$ until it reaches the last smart sensor as a way of identifying the specific fault area and generating isolation (Alonso, 2020).

Another new type of sensor, the stick-on sensor, is available. These sensors are low-cost, self-powered, intelligent, and low-maintenance. As the name suggests, the smart stick-on sensor is attached directly to the smart grid facility to enable automatic monitoring. Different parameters can be monitored by attaching them to busbars, switches, capacitors, transformers, or cables. Each sensor module can act as a network communication node and generate information to interact with neighbouring nodes.

In this scenario, the network uses the ZigBee communication protocol, a low-power, low-cost and reliable protocol that fits the characteristics of the sensors. The radio frequency bands utilized, HZ, are 2.4 GHz (250 kbps), 915 MHz (40 kbps) and 868 MHz (20 kbps) (Moghe, 2011), enabling multi-hop networks, allowing for multiple hops in the node network. To implement a smart stick-on sensor network, coordinator nodes, routers and end devices need to be configured. The smart stick-on sensors are used as end devices. The sensors are in sleep mode for low power consumption and can be activated to perform sensing operations and information processing manually. smart stick-on sensors can be pre-programmed to quickly transmit fault information to the coordinator node when a fault occurs or when the sensor reaches a preset threshold. The data sent by the sensor is timestamped and transmitted from the shortest path to the coordinator using multi-hop communication. The minimum multi-hop path also avoids routing congestion and routing

loops. Routers are used because of reduced signal distortion due to electromagnetic interference and higher received signal strength. On average, one router is required for every 10 nodes (Moghe, 2011).

The power requirement of a sensor is approximately 25 mA (Moghe, 2011), which does not last more than 180 days if a battery is used. The sensor, therefore, needs to rely on ambient energy sources in its surroundings. Of all the environmental energy sources that could potentially be utilized, (IEEE, 2013) shows that magnetic field energy and in some cases, solar energy have proven to be the most suitable environmental energy sources for collection.

6. Internet Base Altering Attack Against Smart Power Grid

A load-altering attack (LAA) is a cyber-physical attack on demand response and demand-side management systems (Amini et al., 2015; Cardenas & Tippenhauer, 2021). Demand response programmes are a new way of managing electricity demand to increase power grid stability and efficiency. Demand-response programmes, in their most basic form, provide consumers with incentives (e.g., through dynamic pricing) to reduce their electricity use during peak hours (Huang et al., 2019). LAA tries to manipulate and modify unsecured controllable loads to cause grid damage through circuit overflow or other negative consequences (Amini et al., 2015). The goal of the attackers is to change the load by using the Internet and automated and distributed software invading agents. These attacks affect the load at the most critical locations in the grid by compromising direct load control command signals, demand-side management price signals, or cloud computation load distribution algorithms to cause

circuit overflow or other malfunctions and damage the power system equipment (Mohsenian-Rad & Leon-Garcia, 2011).

Figure 4. There are three forms of internet-based cyber-attacks against the electric grid. A load-altering cyberattack on the consumer sector is a Type III cyberattack.

Air conditioners, ovens, water heaters, and space heaters are all high-wattage equipment that can now be operated remotely and via the internet, allowing enemies to launch attacks against the electric grid. This means that not all IoT-enabled electrical items allow the attacker to launch this attack (Soltan et al., 2018).

There are two types of LAA:

- *Static Load Altering Attacks*

This is where the attackers are concerned with changing the volume of certain vulnerable loads, abruptly (Amini et al., 2015, 2016, 2018)

- *Dynamic Load Altering Attack*

This is where the attack is concerned with not only the volume but also the trajectory of the changes that are made in the vulnerable load (Amini et al., 2016, 2018)

Three types of loads can be accessed via the Internet and are vulnerable to load-altering attacks.

- *Data Centers and Computation Load*
- *Direct Load Control*
- *Indirect Load Control*

Figure 5. Data centres, direct load control, and automatic energy consumption scheduling units at smart meters are all targets for internet-based load-altering attacks.

Load Altering Attacks can be categorized into three types:

- Attacks that result in frequency instability
- Attacks that cause line failures and result in cascading failures
- Attacks that increase operating costs (Soltan et al., 2018)

6.1. Impact of Internet Base Altering Attack

Local power outages and, in the worst-case scenario, large-scale blackouts can be caused by a Load-Altering Attack (LAA). It can also be used to raise the grid's running costs to benefit a few electrical market utilities (Soltan et al., 2018).

Similarly, attackers can alter a major portion of the load to disrupt the power system, causing inefficiency, economic profit for the attacker, or possibly enough load changes to alter the frequency of the power grid and create wide-scale blackouts (Cardenas & Tippenhauer, 2021).

Finally, LAA attacks can cause the bulk power system to be partitioned, as well as control load shedding (Huang et al., 2019).

6.2. Mitigation of Internet base Altering Attack

One of the features of IoT attacks is that they are widely dispersed and difficult to detect. Once the load has been hacked, the infected devices are unlikely to be taken off the grid (or the Internet) soon after the first attack. As a result, attackers can start a series of attacks, the first of which aims to drive the system into a susceptible condition, followed by an attempt to exploit that vulnerability (Huang et al., 2019).

According to Amini et al. (2018), vulnerable loads can be safeguarded, but at a cost. Adding hardware and software security components, whether at the device level or at the communication level, increases the cost. These costs are borne by utility companies directly and indirectly by end-users. As a result, Amini et al. (2018) offer an approach for calculating

the minimal load that must be safeguarded at each load bus. The *Optimization Problem Formulation* was used to formulate and solve a *non-convex pole placement optimization problem*. The suggested protection method is designed to safeguard enough susceptible loads to keep the system running.

Amini et al. (2016) looked at two scenarios for detecting LAA: detecting LAAs purely based on load signals using a frequency domain analysis and detecting LAAs using a time-domain analysis based on both load and frequency data. According to Amini et al. (2016), depending on the type of attack and the data provided, both time-domain and frequency-domain detection analyses may be required to ensure reliable attack detection.

To sum up, insecure IoT devices can have broad-reaching effects that go far beyond individual security/privacy concerns, according to Soltan et al. (2018). As a result, the security of IoT devices, including legislative frameworks, should be pursued with zeal. System designers and security analysts, according to Soltan et al. (2018), should explicitly analyse vulnerabilities posed by interdependent infrastructure networks such as water, gas, transportation, communication, power grid, and a variety of other networks.

7. Discussion and Future Research

The smart grid is a technology that is constantly maturing and developing. In the not-too-distant future, much research will continue to be conducted to improve this vast network. The government should first focus on researching and developing an information-sharing system that can collect early signals of an attack on the grid and share information that can be used to stop the attack. (Knake, 2017) This work aims to prevent crises before they occur. Modelling the state of the grid will also be a high priority in future research. Although there are already systems available to simulate the state of the grid, the

development of a simulation system for smart grid cybersecurity will remain the focus of future work. This simulation system will not only need to be able to interact and react to the different components within the grid but will also need to exchange information and collaborate with the external environment. (Baumeister, 2010) This system will play a significant role in assessing the cyber security of the system and finding vulnerabilities. In addition, PKI technology, also known as Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), will also be important in future research. In today's grid systems, as mentioned above, there are different communication protocols. Each protocol has its cryptographic requirements. Future research in PKI will focus on the development of a common key that allows for better interoperability between the different cryptographic systems that exist in the system. (Metke & Ekl, 2010)

Finally, in terms of load alteration attacks, attacks may occur in the face of vulnerable load scenarios by disrupting direct load control command signals, indirect load control price signals or cloud computing load allocation algorithms (Mohsenian-Rad & Leon-Garcia, 2011). As protecting vulnerable loads is costly, future research needs to focus on developing cost-effective and cost-efficient load protection strategies.

8. Conclusion

In the modern world of rapid technological development, the energy demand is increasing. This paper focuses on smart grid projects in cyber-physical systems. Although the development of smart grids is still in its infancy worldwide and there is no common precise definition, the role it plays is irreplaceable. Smart grids have significant advantages over conventional grids: they are not only more efficient and stable, but they are also more environmentally friendly and energy-efficient.

All over the world, there is a rapid drive to modernise the grid, i.e., to promote smart grids. At the same time, however, smart grids also face many threats, such as cyber security and physical plant security. This paper also highlights several historical attacks on smart grids and proposes defensive measures such as the use of sensor monitoring to improve the security of smart grids, thus arguing for the importance of smart grid security. Finally, the paper also presents some thoughts and ideas for the future development of smart grids.

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